

THE PROBLEM OF EOSINOPHILIC INFLAMMATION IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE: PREVALENCE, PATHOGENESIS, ROLE IN THE PROGRESSION OF PATHOLOGY AND METHODS OF CORRECTION

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Abstract. *Over the past few decades, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) has become a significant public health concern due to an increase in morbidity and mortality rates. COPD is characterized by reduced airflow velocity due to inflammation of the bronchial tubes and remodeling of small airways. Approximately 20%-40% of patients with COPD experience eosinophilic inflammation in the respiratory tract, similar to that seen in bronchial asthma. Recent studies have shown that eosinophilic COPD represents a distinct condition.*

And it is associated with more significant remodeling of the respiratory tract. Although the exact role of eosinophils in the development of COPD (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) is not fully understood, their level can be used as a prognostic factor and to guide the administration of corticosteroid treatment. Their effectiveness is higher when eosinophil levels are elevated. Therefore, in order to create an effective treatment plan for patients with eosinophilic COPD, it is essential to understand the pathogenesis of this condition. This review will focus on the global prevalence of COPD, the mechanisms behind eosinophil involvement in COPD, how blood and sputum eosinophil counts can be used as biomarkers, and current treatment options for this condition.

Keywords: *chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, eosinophil, inflammation, biomarker, treatment, corticosteroids, cytokine, review, interleukin-5.*

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is one of the most common diseases and a leading cause of respiratory failure, disability, and mortality worldwide. COPD is characterized by progressive and partially irreversible bronchial obstruction due to persistent structural changes, predominantly affecting the distal parts of the respiratory tract and lung parenchyma (1,2,3). Airway obstruction results from chronic inflammation with inflammatory infiltration and edema of the bronchial mucosa, bronchial smooth muscle spasm, peribronchial fibrosis, destruction of lung parenchyma, loss of lung elasticity, and accumulation of secretions in the bronchial lumen (2,3,5).

COPD is a heterogeneous disease that combines various clinical manifestations and pathophysiological mechanisms which predominate to varying degrees and differ in severity among patients. This heterogeneity underlies the classification of COPD patients by phenotype and the individualized therapeutic approach to each patient (6).

As early as the 1990s, researchers noticed that some patients with COPD exhibited elevated levels of eosinophils in their sputum and lung tissue biopsies, both during exacerbations and in stable periods, without a history of bronchial asthma (BA) or atopy (7,8,9). Subsequently, numerous studies revealed a high prevalence of eosinophilic COPD, features of disease progression, and response to therapy in these patients (10,11,12).

Eosinophils are inflammatory leukocytes consisting of bilobed nuclei and large acidophilic cytoplasmic granules. They are produced in healthy bone marrow from CD34+ myeloid precursors (13), and the number of formed eosinophils is usually small, with the level of circulating eosinophils ranging from 1% to 4% of the total leukocyte count in the blood (14). The differentiation of hematopoietic stem cells into mature eosinophils is facilitated by IL-5, while the role of granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor in vivo has been suggested (15,16).

Currently, respiratory tract eosinophilic inflammation is primarily considered not as a criterion for differential diagnosis of BA and COPD or a sign of allergy, but as a characteristic of the phenotype of these lymphocyte nosologies. (17) The analysis of induced sputum made it possible to study the phenotypes of respiratory tract inflammation in BA and COPD. (17) The analysis of induced sputum has made it possible to study the phenotypes of respiratory tract inflammation in asthma and COPD. Previously, eosinophilic inflammation was associated with asthma and was also used in the differential diagnosis of asthma and COPD (18). Eosinophilic inflammation is observed in 19-67% of patients with COPD (19). This indicates the presence of a T2-endotype of inflammation in COPD and asthma (20,21).

The review briefly summarizes the eosinophilic phenotype of COPD, the potential role of blood and sputum eosinophil levels as biomarkers, and the latest treatment methods for eosinophilic COPD currently.

Specificity.

The available data indicate that eosinophilic COPD is a distinct phenotype of the disease with characteristic clinical features and response to GCS treatment (22,23). However, there is no generally accepted definition of eosinophilic COPD, as different researchers have used various criteria and methods for counting eosinophils. Thus, there is no consensus on whether "eosinophilic COPD" is a combination of a specific asthma phenotype in a patient with a history of smoking and fixed airway obstruction, or a true COPD phenotype with an asthmatic immunological profile. Indeed, the presence of eosinophilic inflammation in this group of COPD suggests a similarity to asthma, and eosinophilic COPD was previously considered a component of the "asthma-COPD overlap syndrome" (ACOS) (24,25).

When comparing patients with eosinophilic COPD (blood eosinophil count ≥ 300 cells/ μ l or sputum eosinophils $\geq 3\%$) without a history of asthma and COPD patients with childhood asthma, it was found that patients with COPD and a history of asthma were younger, had more allergic symptoms, and experienced more frequent exacerbations, although in 46% of cases, sputum eosinophil content was $\geq 3\%$, and 36% of them had blood eosinophils ≥ 300 cells/ μ l. Moreover, the median eosinophil count was lower in the COPD group with a history of asthma compared to the COPD group without asthma (220 cells/ μ l versus 420 cells/ μ l; $p=0.001$). Consequently, the different nature of respiratory tract inflammation supports the notion that eosinophilic COPD and COPD with a history of asthma are two separate diseases and should not be combined into the ACOS group (25,26).

Prevalence.

The prevalence of eosinophilic COPD remains uncertain, as different studies used different criteria and eosinophil indicators, but in two COPD patient cohorts, the prevalence was about 15% (27). There is evidence that exacerbations occur more frequently in patients with eosinophilic COPD and those with a history of bronchial asthma (28,29), but this was not confirmed in other studies where an increased blood eosinophil count was not associated with the frequency of severe exacerbations (30). The Copenhagen General Population Study noted an increase in exacerbations when blood eosinophil levels were $>340/\mu\text{L}$ (31), which was also observed in large groups of patients with COPD and in the ECLIPSE study (32).

While blood eosinophil levels are easy to measure in clinical practice, it is unclear whether they reflect eosinophilia in sputum or tissues. Elevated blood eosinophil levels indicate an increase in sputum eosinophils ($>3\%$) in approximately 70% of patients (33), but in COPD patients, there is only a weak correlation between blood and sputum eosinophil counts or bronchial eosinophils (34,35,36).

One challenge is that blood eosinophil counts change over time and even within a single day, so it is important to conduct repeated measurements. In a large COPD patient population, approximately 30% had blood eosinophils $>340/\mu\text{L}$ compared to 25% in healthy individuals, but this increase was unstable, especially in elderly patients (37). In a large population of COPD patients in general practice, blood eosinophil variability was higher with higher eosinophil levels during repeated testing (at least 3 measurements), excluding patients taking oral corticosteroids or antibiotics. In 88% of patients with an initial eosinophil count of $\geq 150/\mu\text{L}$, the subsequent average value was $\geq 150/\mu\text{L}$, while for patients with an initial count of $\geq 300/\mu\text{L}$, 68% had subsequent counts exceeding this level (38). In approximately 15% of COPD patients, blood eosinophil levels consistently exceeded $300/\mu\text{L}$ for 2 years in two large clinical study cohorts (38). Another study showed that 19% of COPD patients had blood eosinophil counts $>300/\mu\text{L}$, and blood eosinophil levels were higher in COPD patients than in the control group, and higher in COPD patients with a history of asthma (39).

Pathogenesis.

The mechanism of eosinophilia development in COPD is not yet clear. An increase in IL-5 content in the sputum of COPD patients with eosinophilia has been reported (40), as well as elevated levels of GM-CSF, which is important for maintaining eosinophil survival in the lungs, and CCL5 (RANTES), which is crucial for attracting eosinophils secreted by respiratory tract epithelial cells (Figure 1) (41). An increase in the number of Th2 and ILC2 cells in the lungs of COPD patients has been described (42, 43). Thymic stromal lymphopoietin (TSLP) and IL-33, cytokines secreted by epithelial cells of COPD patients, may play an important role in attracting and activating Th2 and ILC2 cells (44-46).

Figure-1. Eosinophilic inflammation in COPD. Respiratory tract epithelial cells secrete thymus cytokines - stromal lymphopoietin (TSLP) and interleukin (IL) -33 in response to cigarette smoke and viral infection, which activate T-helpers-2 (Th2) and congenital type 2 lymphoid cells (ILC2), which secrete IL-5, leading to eosinophilic inflammation. Eosinophils can be attracted to the lungs by chemokine CCL5 and retained in the lungs by IL-5 and granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF). Resident eosinophils that are not dependent on IL-5 can also contribute to the development of pulmonary eosinophilia in COPD, but their role is still unknown (47).

Eosinophils contain acidophilic cytoplasmic granules that include various cytokines, chemokines, growth factors, and specific basic proteins, which are highly toxic to bronchial epithelial cells, perpetuate inflammation, and cause tissue damage (48,49). The expression of various surface markers on eosinophils in tissues suggests the existence of eosinophil phenotypes with different regulatory functions (50). In healthy individuals, eosinophils are not found in the airways, and their presence indicates an abnormal inflammatory response (51). It remains unclear why only a minority of patients with COPD exhibit pronounced eosinophilia, but this may be related to the fact that some COPD patients have significant eosinophilia due to coexisting allergies or asthma.

Treatment.

The question of whether blood or sputum eosinophilia can affect the effectiveness of inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) in COPD patients is of significant interest (52). Treatment of COPD patients with elevated eosinophils in their sputum using increased doses of ICS led to a decrease in exacerbations (53), and oral corticosteroids reduced elevated IL-5 levels in sputum (54). Subsequent analysis showed that elevated levels of eosinophils in the blood are associated with a greater effect of ICS in reducing exacerbations and slowing disease progression, although it is ineffective for treating lung function or symptoms (55-59). In the largest subsequent analysis of 3 studies ($n = 4528$), which compared formoterol alone with a combination of budesonide and formoterol, a consistent relationship was found between blood eosinophil count and reduction in exacerbation frequency with ICS use, while no benefit was observed when the eosinophil count was $<100/\mu\text{l}$ (60). This study, unlike others, did show some improvement in FEV1 and quality of life with ICS. However, other studies did not confirm these results, as an increase in blood eosinophil levels did not predict a better effect in reducing exacerbations during treatment with long-acting β 2-agonists (LABA) compared to the bronchodilator combination of long-acting muscarinic antagonists (LAMA) and LABA (61). However, the difference between LABA and

LABA-LAMA and ICS-LABA levels was lower when blood eosinophil content was $\geq 300/\mu\text{l}$. Additionally, in COPD patients with a history of severe exacerbations despite treatment with ICS, LAMA, and LABA, there was no increase in exacerbations after ICS discontinuation, except when blood eosinophil levels were $\geq 4\%$ (62-64). The general consensus is that if blood eosinophil levels are $>300/\mu\text{l}$ or $>4\%$, ICS treatment may lead to a further reduction in exacerbation frequency when added to LABA and LAMA therapy, and such patients may benefit from these drugs prescribed as fixed-dose triple combination inhalers (65-66).

Recent studies using fixed-dose triple combination inhalers containing corticosteroids, LABA, and LAMA have confirmed that the triple combination showed a greater decrease in blood eosinophil levels compared to the LABA-LAMA combination in patients with blood eosinophil levels $\geq 2\%$ or $\geq 150/\mu\text{l}$ (67-69). However, there is still uncertainty whether elevated blood eosinophil levels indicate elevated lung eosinophil levels in patients receiving LABA-LAMA combination therapy for COPD and whether it might be a biomarker for other effects of ICS on exacerbations.

The increasing evidence that blood eosinophils are associated with ICS response in COPD suggests they are a convenient biomarker for more personalized therapy. This was recognized in the recent update of the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD 2019). Previously, the choice of COPD pharmacotherapy was based on exacerbation history and symptoms (70). In the latest edition, ICS is indicated only for patients with frequent exacerbations and symptoms (GOLD D) if blood eosinophil levels are $\geq 300/\mu\text{l}$ (71). If symptoms and exacerbations persist, additional therapy is required (72). It is recommended that if exacerbations persist despite LAMA and LABA therapy, ICS should be added as triple therapy if blood eosinophil levels are $\geq 100/\mu\text{l}$. However, if exacerbations persist despite ICS treatment, ICS should be discontinued if blood eosinophil levels are less than $300/\mu\text{l}$. If exacerbations still continue, roflumilast or azithromycin can be added to triple therapy, or LAMA + LABA therapy can be used if blood eosinophil levels are $\leq 100/\mu\text{l}$ (Figure 2).

Figure-2. Significance of blood eosinophils in determining COPD therapy. If exacerbations persist after initial therapy with long-acting $\beta 2$ -agonists (LABA) or long-acting muscarinic antagonists (LAMA), a combination of inhalation corticosteroids (ICS) and LABA is indicated at blood eosinophil levels $\geq 100/\mu\text{l}$, while at blood eosinophil levels < 100 , a combination

of LABA and LAMA is recommended. If the exacerbations continue, a triple combined inhaler can be indicated if the blood level of eosinophils is ≥ 100 . If patients receiving IGCS continue to experience exacerbations, IGCS can be discontinued if the blood level of eosinophils is ≤ 300 . In patients with ongoing disease exacerbation, oral roflumylast or azithromycin, or a combination of LABA-LAMA with a blood eosinophil level ≤ 100 , can be added to triple inhalation therapy. (Adapted according to GOLD 2019) (73). This is a heterogeneous disease - in terms of symptoms, physiology, inflammation, extrapulmonary effects, treatment reactions, and disease progression, therefore patients' reactions to treatment vary.

Conclusions.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is characterized by chronic inflammation of the lungs and an increased number of inflammatory cells in the sputum. In some patients with COPD, there is an increase in the amount of eosinophils in the sputum, which is characteristic of bronchial asthma, and this can manifest as an increase in the number of eosinophils in the blood. Elevated levels of eosinophils in blood and sputum can indicate more frequent exacerbations and a favorable response to ICS to prevent exacerbations, as well as a good response to systemic corticosteroids during exacerbations. The mechanisms of development of eosinophilic COPD have not been sufficiently studied, and treatment with drugs against IL-5 apparently does not have a significant positive effect in preventing exacerbations in such patients. Further research is needed to link inflammation endotypes to clinical outcomes and reactions to more precise anti-inflammatory drugs. Currently, methods for treating inflammation are being developed. (74.75).

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